

Exploring Methods for Measuring Audience Body Motion in Concert Halls - Supplementary Material

Hugh A. von Arnim (hughav@uio.no)¹²

Finn Upham (finnu@uio.no)¹²

Alexander Refsum Jensenius (alexanje@uio.no)¹²

¹RITMO Centre for Interdisciplinary Studies in Rhythm, Time, and Motion, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway

²Department of Musicology, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway

1. Introduction

This document contains the supplementary material for the paper “Exploring Methods for Measuring Audience Body Motion in Concert Halls” submitted to the Sound and Music Computing conference 2026.

The contents are as follows. Section 2 provides a more extensive description of the data types used in the paper. Section 3 shows the individual time series plotted in the time domain for each signal type and participant, both unprocessed and cleaned/normalised. Section 4 shows the plots describing the clock jitter of the devices. Section 5 shows the spatial frequency decompositions for the thermal(B) and thermal(D) data types to demonstrate the effect of the device internal image processing in the thermal box camera. Section 6 shows the correlations for low motion areas of the recordings. Section 7 shows plots of QoM across data types for applause. Section 8 details the method for obtaining respiration signals from the accelerometers.

2. Data Types

In the following, we outline the principles, advantages, and limitations of each of the data types.

2.1 RGB

RGB imaging employs an image sensor that measures the intensity of light in the visible range of the electromagnetic spectrum in three broad, overlapping spectral bands corresponding to red, green, and blue light. This is commonly achieved using a sensor array overlaid with a colour filter, after which the signals are interpolated to produce three colour channels per pixel. The resulting video data consists of three channels of pixel intensity values at the spatial resolution of the camera, commonly stored at 8 bits per channel in compressed video formats.

2.2 IR

IR imaging employs an image sensor that measures the intensity of light in the near-infrared range of the electromagnetic spectrum. This means that it is commonly used to record the

intensity of the infrared radiation *reflected* rather than *emitted* within a scene, therefore requiring active illumination with an infrared light source. The resulting video data is a single channel of 8-bit greyscale values at the spatial resolution of the camera, however in common compressed video formats this is usually encoded using standard three-channel pixel encoding formats (e.g. YUV), meaning that there is a lot of redundant information stored.

2.3. Thermal Temperature Data

Thermal temperature measurement usually employs a microbolometer sensor array that measures the intensity of mid- or long-wave electromagnetic radiation. Unlike near-infrared imaging, this is *emitted* by objects related to their surface area rather than *reflected*. Therefore no active illumination of a scene is required. The measured intensity at the sensor is mapped into an absolute temperature measurement based upon calibration and assumptions about the emissivity of the surface --- that is the ratio between the amount of thermal radiation emitted by a surface and an idealised blackbody that would emit the maximum amount of thermal radiation at a given temperature (Vollmer and Möllmann 2018: 31) --- and its distance to the camera. The resulting data is not compressed into an image format, therefore consisting of a two-dimensional array of temperature measurements as numerical values (e.g. 16- or 32-bit floating point) sampled pixel-to-pixel at the spatial resolution of the sensor. However, due to the thermal time constant of the microbolometer sensor --- its response speed to a change in intensity of thermal radiation (Vollmer and Möllmann 2018: 112) --- rapid motion can result in a "smearing" of fast moving objects.

2.4 Thermal Imaging

Thermal imaging is the mapping of the thermal higher bit depth temperature data into an 8-bit monochrome image format. Various styles of colourmap can be employed, and a maximum and minimum temperature for the mapping range can either be set prior to the image generation (in effect clipping the thermal data into a specific range) or adapted frame-wise based upon the maximum and minimum temperatures within each frame. It is therefore usually not possible to infer absolute temperature information from a thermal image without a colourbar showing the mapping range. However, when less interested in using the thermal image for absolute temperature measurement but rather motion analysis, the inclusion of a colourbar becomes less important, especially when changing elements of an onscreen display in an adaptive mapping between frames can distort motion measurement. The resultant data is usually provided in an encoded video format, and similar to the IR, there can be redundant data due to the duplication of channels depending upon the colourmap chosen (i.e. a greyscale colourmap will duplicate channels, but a blue to orange colourmap will require a three-channel pixel representation). Usually the thermal images are post-processed within the camera to preserve, for example, contrast levels when mapping high bit-depth data into lower bit-depth representations. Therefore, a direct output of a frame of thermal data into an image will not exactly match the same frame in the thermal image. Using thermal imaging for motion analysis in a style similar to the QoM measure is gaining traction in fields such as biology (e.g. Tattersall et al. 2020).

2.5 Accelerometer Data

Triaxial accelerometer sensor capture force exerted on the device in three orientations. In normal operating conditions at rest, gravity is a constant force downward against the

dimension of the sensor. Accelerometers also capture additional forces producing displacement, reflecting changes in absolute velocity, direction of motion, and rotation. Accelerometers can record at much higher rates than camera systems, supporting higher precision timing information. In this study, the accelerometer sensors were set to record values at around 400Hz. Accelerometer sensors are a common component of many sensing devices, including mobile phones, as well as available as light weight stand-alone wearable units (the AX3s are 15g) that can be worn on a person in a variety of ways. In an audience measurement context, a single well placed accelerometer can pick up a variety of actions and body rhythms, including heart beats (ballistocardiography), respiration, posture changes, and large limb displacements (clapping, stomping). However, these signals are not consistently visible in accelerometer time series, depending on how the body itself is positioned and whether it is in motion.

The accelerometers used in this study, Axivity AX3 sensors, had been well worn from over a decade of use, and some artifacts in the measurements reflect poor calibration between the three axes measured. They also did not maintain a consistent sample rate, ranging around 400Hz. As such, their sensor values had to be resampled before feature extraction and analysis.

Acceleration magnitude was calculated on the 400 Hz resampled sensor measurements without normalisation. Jerk at that frequency is not interpretable, so each dimension of the acceleration recordings were filtered and downsampled to 10Hz before the magnitude of difference was calculated per device.

3. Quantity of Motion Time Series

This section includes the individual plots of the QoM time series for each participant and each signal type.

3.1 Initial

The following are the QoM time series for each datatype and participant before cleaning/normalisation. GOP spikes are visible in encoded video formats.

3.1.1 RGB

3.1.2 IR

3.1.3 Thermal(P)

3.1.4 Thermal(B)

3.1.5 Thermal(D)

3.1.6 |ACC| (400Hz)

3.1.7 |Jerk| (400Hz)

3.2 Cleaned and Normalised

The following are the QoM time series for each datatype and participant before cleaning/normalisation. Each signal was assessed for measurement artifacts, cleaned of those systematically separable from the signal, and then range normalised by participant, from 10% to 98%. Matching at the extremes is justified by the irregular movement being captured, with long intervals of little motion and two rounds of applause. This normalisation is to assist the assessment of the visibility of audience motion against sensor noise, even if the energy of these motions may vary between participants.

To facilitate direct comparison between measurement systems and signals, 10 Hz resamplings of each time series were generated, filtering and downsampling (and in one case upsampling) to have aligned values from each signal per person. 10 Hz is faster than the rate at which humans can generate limb motion, and has been used for audience motion analysis before.

3.2.1 RGB

The quantity of motion measurements had to be cleaned of I-frame distortions. These Panasonic cameras maintained a consistent frame rate and I-frame rate. The prominence of the I-frame distortions on QoM depends on the proportion of signal to noise in the frames being assessed. A scene with very little change will show I frames very clearly. A scene with lots of visible movements can cover some of these encoding artifacts. In this case, the lighting conditions were so dark that frame wise differences were mostly noise and showed the I-frame peaks and tailing change quite strongly.

To assess the cyclical effect of each I-frame on the quantity of motion, a template of distortion was constructed from the median values by frame number (relative to Iframes) across the whole recording, shown above. These median values were then subtracted from the QoM of each group of pictures. The median is relatively robust to the “outlier” motion signals and produce a balanced impact across the time series, half raising and half lowering the frame-wise QoM. The stability of the encoding artifacts made this evaluation and cleaning very easy.

3.2.2 IR

Recorded from the same type of device and with similar video encoding settings, the Infrared camera QoM measurements were cleaned with the same procedure as the RGB camera. The I-frames were spaced consistently and showed a robust median sequence even though more motion was visible to this recording system from the infrared lamp coverage.

Since the illumination by the lamp was uneven across participants, as is often the case in real concert conditions, noise scaling with normalisation is a point of interest.

3.2.3 Thermal(P)

The thermal cameras all had frame rate inconsistencies, sometimes skipped frames, sometimes doubled. As a result, the I-frame rate was also inconsistent. As such building and subtracting a median encoding template was impractical. However, the thermal videos also had much stronger motion signals than the RGB and IR cameras, leaving the peaks of I-frames visible but covering the subsequent encoding artifacts in frame-wise QoM. The (mostly) 25 Hz QoM time series from the Thermal pocket camera were cleaned with a 3 sample rolling median filter.

3.2.4 Thermal(B)

As explained for Thermal(P), a rolling median filter was used to clean these (mostly) 50 Hz quantity of motion time series per participant.

3.2.5 Thermal(D)

The thermal data had no I-frame related issues as it was never compressed. Frame-wise differences per crop of each participant were only normalised and upsampled to 10 hz for comparison with the other measurements.

3.2.6 |ACC|

The accelerometers were supposed to be collected at 400 Hz. The actual sample rate varied surprisingly, though always in the hundreds of samples per second. Each measurement was resampled within each triaxial dimension before magnitude of acceleration was calculated per sample. The |ACC| QoM signal was not filtered, except in the 10 Hz form.

3.2.7 |Jerk|

First-order differenced jerk magnitude on the 400Hz sample was mostly sensor noise. Calculating jerk magnitude on a 10 hz acceleration values showed more relevant variation. So these Jerk values were constructed from low-pass (2nd order, Butterwork, 10 Hz cut off) filtered sensor values and downsampling before normalisation.

4. Device Clock Jitter

The following plots show the clock jitter as obtained from probing the data directly offloaded from the device. For each RGB, IR, Thermal(P), and Thermal(B), the top plot shows the frame intervals as reported by video metadata timestamps, whereas the bottom plot shows the interval between the actual presentation of the frames in video as reported by the PresentationTimeStamps (PTS). For Thermal(D) the plot shows the interval between frames as reported by the packet header metadata.

4.1 Panasonic HC-X2000 (RGB)

4.2 IPanasonic HC-X2000 (IR)

4.3 HIKMICRO Pocket Thermography Camera HM-TP42-3AQF/W-Pocket2 (Thermal(P))

4.4 HIKMICRO Thermographic Network Box Camera HM-TD2067T-25/X (Thermal(B))

4.5 HIKMICRO Thermographic Network Box Camera HM-TD2067T-25/X (Thermal(D))

5. Thermal Imaging/Data Spatial Frequency Components

The following plots show the spatial decomposition of the highlighted regions A1 and A2 at frame t of Figure 2 in the accompanying paper. These were obtained by taking the Discrete Cosine Transform of the region, and are used to highlight the effect of the device internal image filtering, in particular the Digital Detail Enhancement (DDE), applied when mapping the high precision thermal data to a low precision image format. The plots show the spatial spectra of Thermal(B) with DDE filtering (left) and Thermal(D) (middle) along with their spectral difference (right). A boost in the mid-to-high frequency bands in Thermal(B) is visible, while the highest frequency bands corresponding to noise are suppressed.

5.1 A1

5.1.1 All Spatial Frequency Components

5.1.2 First 20 Spatial Frequency Components

5.2 A2

5.2.1 All Spatial Frequency Components

5.1.2 First 20 Spatial Frequency Components

6. Low Motion correlations

To compare how these features captured moments of very low motion, the 10Hz samplings of QoM were further filtered and downsampled to 1Hz to cut through sensor noise for intervals without identifiable movements by the participants. These reduced features were clipped to the bottom third of values per feature. Below shows when there was the low QoM according to each feature (lighter shade), and their evident disagreement.

7. Clapping

Applause examples

QoM during Claps1 for AU5

QoM during Claps1 for AU7

8. Respiration signal extraction and evaluation

Without reduction to magnitude, the accelerometer measurements from over the rib cage showed oscillations around the expected respiration rate in one or two (or no) dimensions. Empirical Mode Decomposition was used to extract likely frequency components using masking noise (frequencies banding [30, 12, 3, 0.3, 0.05, 0.005]). Example below. Likely respiration sequences were recomposed of the 4th and 5th IMFs.

Analysis of the decomposed components show clear respiration like qualities as well as good agreement between dimensions when more than one carried a noticeable respiration signal. Below are phase onsets and breath-wise features extracted from these oscillations by a respiration feature extraction library (respy) from two dimensions of AU1's accelerometer sensor. The signal disappears during the initial and final applause interval, but between the cycle rates match expected respiratory behaviour during attentive listening, including breaths with a shorter inspiration phase and stability over time.

While some cycles caught may be artifacts of other motions and should be cleaned carefully before testing any given respiratory feature, there is a persistent respiration signal captured in most participants from this sensor placement. Representative signals from each of the 5 with measurable respiration presented together below.

